

ECONOMIC ANALYSES OF SMALL HOLDER FARMERS: A CASE STUDY OF MAIZE
FARMERS IN KOGI STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the economic analysis of maize production in Kogi State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to identify the socio-economic characteristics of the respondent, to estimate cost and returns, efficiency of resource use, and input-output relationship. Primary data were used for the study. They were obtained through interview schedule. A total of 500 households engaged in maize production were investigated. Data collated were analyzed using descriptive statistics, budgetary analysis, multiple regression analysis and resource use efficiency models. Results from the analyses revealed that majority of the farmers were above productive age, were experienced and have the ability to read and write. The regression analysis showed that variable inputs such as fertilizer, quantity of seed, agro chemical, farm size and years of experience, significantly affect maize production in the study area. Significant input variables are determinants of maize production in the study area.

Empirical result also revealed that maize production is viable with about 40% return in investment for every N1 invested in the maize farming enterprise. Resource use efficiency in the study area showed under utilization for seed, farm size, fertilizer and agro chemicals.

KEYWORDS: Agriculture, Farmers, Maize, Production.

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INTRODUCTION

At independence in 1960, agriculture was the mainstay of the Nigerian Economy, contributing over 50% of the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and serving as the main source of export and foreign exchange for the country. Between 1960-1969, agriculture contributed 58.7% of the GDP, with the figure declining to 33.2% between 1970 and 1974. Only 2.5% of the GDP was accounted for by the manufacturing sector during the same period (1970-1974). The country then was basically agrarian and agriculture accounted for 80% of employment (Zanna, 2000).

The primary engine of growth in the agricultural sector then was export of tradable agricultural products that were the major sources of government revenue and foreign exchange. In recent years, and particularly after the civil war, there has been more rapid increase in food prices leading to greater emphasis on the promotion of food crops. At the same time, the dependence of the Nigerian economy on agricultural exports for foreign exchange is being relieved by the oil industry providing government the alternative revenue source to pursue other non agricultural objectives.

Besides, other agricultural policies that have been implemented after the colonial era addressed agricultural credit, farm input and subsidy; agricultural mechanisation; agricultural pricing and marketing; and agricultural research.

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According to Osemeobo (1992), the major programmes implemented to promote agricultural development in Nigeria include; National Accelerated Food Production Programme; Operation Feed the Nation (OFN); Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGS); Green Revolution (GR); River Basin Development Authority (RBDA); Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure; National Agricultural Land Development Authority; Agricultural Development Projects (ADP) among others:

Despite various efforts to stimulate agricultural production in Nigeria, agricultural productivity has been declining over the years with production costs that are unacceptably high while food that is adequate in quantity and quality cannot be afforded by many Nigerians (Ugwu, 1990 and Ekpebu, 2001). Ukeji (2000) also described agricultural productivity, which has been growing over the years at different rates, as low.

Many farm level studies (Norman, 1973; Nwosu, 1975; Osuji, 1978; Akpan, 1982 and Onyewaku, 1989) have attested to low resource productivity and economic efficiency in Nigerian agriculture. They ascribe this to the structure of agricultural activities in terms of small uneconomic units, predominance of traditional techniques of production, excessive fragmentation of holdings and consequently little mechanisation of farm operations, limited use of agro-chemicals, high dependence on traditional storage and marketing facilities and inadequate supply of credit with its attendant low productivity and income. Similar studies carried out on productivity of resources indicated that small farmers are often time allocatively efficient in resource use given their levels of technology (Schultz, 1964; Hopper, 1965; Singh, 1975; and Kassie *et al*, 1999). But Olagoke (1990) noted that, the suggestion by Ogunfowora *et al* (1974); Mijindad *i*(1980); and Shapiro (1983) that the efficiency hypotheses also apply to most of the small farmers cannot be overemphasized.

Studies (Idachaba, 1981; Etuk, 1979) have indicated that labour is still the most precious possession of the small farmers. Yet, little research has been carried out on various aspect of farm labour in traditional agriculture: labour utilization and labour profiles in different crops and ecological zones, the structure of farm labour markets, the linkages between rural farm labour markets and non-farm labour markets, supply and demand relations in farm labour. Not only that, the small holder farmers often cultivate between 0.1 - 5 hectares (Oranyeli, 1979) using their cutlass and hoes which have since ceased to offer any attraction to the youths. Etuk (1979) further observed that the problem of labour, as one of the most constraining resources in farm level productivity, becomes more apparent at peak periods of production as a result of the introduction of modern inputs and rural-urban migration which has depopulated the country side.

In spite of these multi-faceted problems that bedevil the overall performance of the smallholder farmers, it has been pointed out that they account for about 95 per cent of agricultural outputs of most crops grown in Nigeria (Oyaide, 1979; Olayide, 1980; Olayemi, 1980). Also, available studies (Olayide, 1976; World Bank, 1981) indicate that smallholder farmers account for 80 per cent of the agricultural outputs in most African countries. According to Reynolds (1975), evidence from other countries such as Columbia and India indicate that smallholder farmers and their families not only utilize more labour and other agricultural inputs but more importantly achieve higher yields per hectare. Similarly, White, 1981 in his study 'Green Revolution Programme in South East Asia' shows that while small-scale farmers were not limited by lack of access to improved technologies and extension services, they rapidly adopted agricultural innovations and produced higher yields per hectare than the large scale farmers.

The objective of this study is to examine the social economic characteristics maize farmers, to determine the efficiency of resource use and the viability of production in the study area.

Research Questions

- (i) What are the socio-economic characteristics that affect maize production?
- (ii) How efficient are resources being utilized in the production of maize in Kogi State?
- (iii) What are the constraints in maize production in the study area?

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

Kogi State is found in the central region of Nigeria. It is popularly called the Confluence State because the confluence of River Niger and River Benue is at its capital, Lokoja, which is the first administrative capital of modern-day Nigeria. The state was formed in 1991 from parts of Kwara State and Benue State. Agriculture is the mainstay of the economy and the principal cash crops. The state is known for its mass production of farm produce such coffee, cocoa, palm oil, cashews, groundnuts, maize, cassava, yam, rice and melon. According to 2005 estimate, Kogi State has approximate population of 3,595,789. Kogi State has a coordinate of 7°30'N6°42'E and a land area 29,833 km²

Fig. 1: Kogi State Map showing all the local governments
Source: Google Map

Kogi State has an average maximum temperature of 33.2°C and average minimum of 22.8°C. The state has two distinct weather conditions, dry season, which lasts from November to February and rain season that lasts from March to October. Annual rainfall ranges from 1016mm to 1524mm.

Methodology

The study was conducted in Kogi State of Nigeria. Farming is the major occupation of the majority of the people in the locality. The study employed multi-stage sampling technique involving a purposive selection of eight maize producing clans that are chiefly concerned with maize production as their most preferred means of livelihood in the study areas. A total of four hundred questionnaires were utilized for detailed study.

Data was collected using a well structured questionnaire and interview schedule administered on the respondents. Data collections covered one production cycle and include input-output data such as farm size, family labour, hired labour and planting material, capital, maize output, price and quantity sold, as well as socio-economic characteristics of respondent. A combination of descriptive Sampling Technique

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Analytical Technique

Tools such as descriptive statistics, gross margin analysis, and production function were applied to the data collated.

Descriptive Statistics

Frequencies and percentages ratios were employed in order to address the objective on socio-economic characteristics of the farmer as well as the constraints associated with maize production.

Gross Margin Analysis

Gross margin analysis by definition is the difference between the gross farm income and total variable cost (Olukosi and Erhabor, 1988). Normally, gross margin analysis is used to test the effects of changes that do not alter the fixed cost of production, especially the cost of land and other durable factors. It is used to determine the potential profitability on farmer's farm income. It has the advantage of being simple as well as useful in the analysis of the profitability of small farms that have small fixed costs (Samm, 2009).

The gross margin was estimated from costs and returns in maize production. The Gross model can be expressed as;

$$GM = TR - TVC$$

Where:

GM = Gross margin (₦/ha)

TR = Total revenue or total value of output from the maize enterprise (₦/ha). This is the product of average output per hectare multiplied by the market price. An open market price of 2012 was used during the computation.

TVC = Total variable cost or the costs that are specific in producing (Maize) output (₦/ha).

TVC varies according to output and are incurred on variable inputs. This includes cost of inputs like seeds, fertilizer, and harvesting, processing, labour cost (hired/family).

Efficiency Ratio

Efficiency is generally defined as the quantity of output (*Y*) per unit of input (*X*) used in the production process, that is, the average physical productivity (APP).

In order to ascertain whether resources were efficiently utilized, the marginal value product (MVP) of the variable inputs used was computed and compared with their input prices. The following ratio was used to compute the efficiency of resource use.

$$R = \frac{MVP}{MFC}$$

Where:

R = Efficiency ratio

MVP = Marginal value product (value addition in maize output due to the use of additional unit of input)

MFC = Marginal factor cost (unitcost of a particular resource used).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Social Economic characteristics

The social-economic factors of interest in this study are; age distribution of the farmers, gender, education, membership of association, experience and family size. These have been represented in frequency table and shown in Table 1.

Empirical results show that majority farmers are between the age of 46 years old and above (80%) were more involved in maize production in the study area. The average age of the respondents is 46.97. Age is an important

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determinant of social – economic status of a population since people wear in energy as they advance in age. Therefore, these generally aged maize farmers could have negative implications on the future of maize cultivation in the study area.

Table 1: Social Economic Characteristics

Variable	Description	Frequency	Percentage
Age of Respondent	≤ 30	13.2	3.3
	31 – 45	66.8	16.7
	46 – 55	216.8	54.2
	≥55	103.2	25.8
	Total	400.0	100.0
Gender	Male	350.0	87.5
	Female	50.0	12.5
	Total	400.0	100.0
Education Status	No formal education	150.0	37.5
	Primary education	136.8	34.2
	Secondary Education	70.0	17.5
	Tertiary education	36.8	9.2
	Quaranic education	6.8	1.7
	Total	400.0	100.0
Membership of cooperative society	Yes	380.0	95.0
	No	20.0	5.0
	Total	400.0	100.0
Major Source of Fund	Personal	356.8	89.2
	Money lender	10.0	2.5
	Bank loan	6.8	1.7
	Cooperative/interv. fund	26.8	6.7
	Total	400.0	100.0
Years of Experience	≤ 10	118	29.6
	11 – 20	215	53.7
	21 – 30	56	13.9
	≥ 31	11	2.8
	Total	400	100.0

Source: Data Analysis, 2012.

Table 1 also suggests that maize production dominated by males in the study area as about 87.50% of the respondents are male. This can be attributed to the fact that men always have right to land as a productive resource than women. Quisumbing (1994), reported that there has been a great disparity between women and men in the size of landholdings and that the mode of women participation in agricultural production varies with the land-owning status of households. The male domination of male farming may also be due to high demands of time and energy required to work in such enterprise. This agrees with the study of Baiyegunhi and Fraser, (2009).

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The study shows that 37.5% of the farmers had no formal education, while about 62.5% farmers have one form of formal education or the other. This implies that maize farmers in the study area are generally knowledgeable. Education is regarded as an investment in human capital, which is able to raise the skill and quality of the man, narrow his information gaps and increase his locative efficiency thereby leading to more productive performance. Therefore, introduction of new ideas and adoption of new innovations and technology into the study areas will be easy. This will in turn increase yield, income and agricultural production in general.

More than half of the farmers (53.7%) have been producing maize for upwards of 11-20 years, while about (29.6%) have at most 10 years of experience. It can therefore be inferred that majority of the farmers are experienced maize growers. Credit facility was predominantly by personal savings (89.2%). Only about 1.7% and 6.7% respectively borrowed money from bank and cooperative society to finance their farming activities.

This situation calls for urgent interventions by stake holders in the agricultural sectors.

Determinant of Maize Production

Ordinary least square (OLS) estimate of the parameters which show the average performance of the maize farming households in the study area is presented in Table 2. The high value of adjusted R^2 implies that about 82.90 percent of the variation in the production process was explained by the various explanatory variables/inputs employed. Some of the coefficients of the measured parameters such as farm size, labour, agro chemicals, fertilizers and seed were statistically significant and exhibited expected sign. These significant variables are determinant of maize production in the study area. Years of experience exhibit negative sign. This is not unconnected with the fact that most farmers in the study area are relatively old as seen earlier in farmers' characteristics.

Table 2: OLS estimate of Cobb-Douglass production function

Variable	Parameters	Coefficient	T-ratio	Coefficient	T-ratio
Constant	β_0	-4.3835	-4.0200*	-1.8310	-0.5500
Farm size	β_1	0.7888	4.9200*	0.8807	2.5900*
Agro chemicals	β_2	0.0586	2.2600*	1.0220	4.1600*
Seed	β_3	0.2618	3.1300*	0.2036	1.0100*
Years of Exp.	β_4	-0.1652	-2.0200*	-0.5888	-1.1800*
Family labour	β_5	0.0206	0.3900	0.1264	1.9700*
Hired labour	β_6	0.0493	-0.9100	0.6302	2.7300*
Fertilizer	β_7	0.1277	-3.2100*	0.1963	1.3400*

$R^2_{adj}=86.65$, *significant at 1% level.

Costs and Returns Analysis

A gross return was calculated by multiplying the total quantity of produce harvested by the price of output sold. The result is as presented in Table 3. The gross return per one hectare in maize production in the study area was ₦80,701.42. For cost of production, total variable cost and total fixed cost were considered in order to calculate the total cost of production. The total variable cost includes cost of labour, chemicals, fertilizer and seeds while total fixed costs includes cost of renting/borrowing land, and depreciation on farm tools. The straight line method, which assumed a constant rate of annual depreciation, was used to calculate the depreciation on farm tools.

The labour used consists of family, hired and group labour. The wage rate varies slightly depending on the operation to be performed on the farm. The average wage rate of ₦850.00 per man-day was used to calculate the total labour cost. The total cost of labour per hectare was ₦27,826.54. This cost accounted for 54.5% of the total of production. Labour generally is noted to be one the most important factor of production especially when it comes to farming experiment. This could be one of the reasons why more than half of the variable cost went

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to labour alone. Another reason could be non availability or scarcity of labour. Fertilizer accounts for about 25.3% of the production cost. While Agro chemicals accounts for 15.7% of the total variable cost.

For the purpose of yield and good output, the importance of fertilizers and agro chemicals cannot be over emphasize. This could be why more than a quarter of the variable cost went for either of these very important inputs. Baiyegunhi and Fraser (2009) have observed that in order to increase yield, seed dressing chemicals such as herbicides and pesticides that prevent undue exposure of cultivated seed to fungal attacked must be used.

The gross margin and net farm income (profit) per hectare were ₦80,701.42 and ₦91,416.67. The rate of return on investment was 140%. These imply that for every ₦1 invested into the maize farming enterprise in Kogi State, ₦1.40 was made as revenue. That is, about 40 kobo is realized as profit. The rate of return on capital invested estimate (RORCI), otherwise called efficiency level is 0.40. This suggest profitability and viability of maize farming in Kogi State as this value is higher than lending rate of between 6 – 25% charged by both cooperative society and commercial banks in the study area.

Table 3: Gross margin and returns in investment/acre

Item	Amount (₦)
Total Revenue	80,701.42
Labour	27,826.54(54.6)
Cost of chemicals	8,013.99(15.7)
Cost of fertilizer	12,907.63(25.3)
Cost of seed	2,262.50(4.4)
Total variable cost	51,010.66
Gross margin	29,690.76
Fixed cost/depreciation*	6,760.49
Net Farm Income/Profit (NFI)	22,930.27
Rate of Return on investment (ROR)	1.40 (140%)
Efficiency level/(RORCI)(%)	0.40 (40%)

*Depreciation is based on average annual linear depreciation for all equipments including land.

Author's analysis based on data collected from the field

Figures in parenthesis are percentage of variable cost

Efficiency of Resource Use

The role of efficiency in increasing agricultural output has been duly recognized by both researchers and policy makers (Omonona *et al* 2010)

In determining the efficiency of inputs used, Marginal Value Product and the Marginal Factor Cost (MVP and MFC) were estimated. The marginal factor cost which is the unit price for the variable inputs used for maize production in the study areas were estimated as ₦7,500, ₦4,500, ₦4560 and ₦850 for seed, farm size, fertilizer and chemical respectively. This result is as presented in Tables 4

Seed input is being employed below economic optimum level as indicated by its efficiency ratio 244.35. It is therefore rational to increase the quantity of seed as this will bring about a corresponding increase in total value product of about ₦1,832.60.

Fertilizer was also seen to be under utilized as shown by its value of efficiency ratio. This suggests that with other inputs held constant, increasing fertilizer by one kilogram would increase total value product by ₦893.90. Other inputs were also seen to be currently under utilized. It is therefore economical to increase the use of these inputs for optimal return in investment in the study area. Hence resource use adjustment and optimal combination of these parameters should be adopted by farmers in the study area.

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Table 4: Resource use efficiency for maize production in Kogi State

Resource	MPP(Kg)	Unit price of input(N'000)	MVP(N)	MFC(N'000)	R=MVP/MFC
Seed	0.2618	7.50	1832.60	7.50	244.35
Farm Size	0.7888	45.00	5521.60	45.00	122.70
Fertilizer	0.1277	4.56	893.90	4.56	196.03
Chemical	0.0586	0.85	410.20	0.85	482.59

Source: field survey, 2012.

CONCLUSION

The study examined economic analyses maize farmers in Kogi State. Primary data was basically used for the study and this was obtained using stratified sampling technique, and through interview.

The study revealed that majority of the farmers 70% are above productive ages, and that maize production was mainly dominated by male with majority of the farmers (65%) having the ability to read and write.

Empirical result also revealed that maize production is more viable with about 40% return in investment for every N1 invested in the maize farming enterprise. Resource use efficiency in the study area showed under utilization for seed, farm size, fertilizer and agro chemicals.

Maize production was found to be viable and profitable under efficient management. Maize potentials in terms of yield and quality of the product have not been fully exploited. Consequently, there is still deficit supply of maize in the country. This could be adduced to inaccessibility of the farmers to the appropriate modern technology and modern innovations such as improved seeds, fertilizer, adequate credit/fund and adequate extension services. This poses serious threat in the general food supply in the future, if nothing is done to correct the imbalance in maize production.

To increase maize production, it is therefore necessary for individuals, government and non- governmental organization to assist maize farmers in order to improve maize production in the study area and Nigeria in general.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. Farmers in the study area should be provided with inputs such as seed, fertilizer, agrochemicals and services of qualified extension workers. This is to enable them become more efficient in maize production and further guarantee food security.
- ii. Improved technologies that can guarantee sustainable and continuous maize production all year round should be extended to farmers for adoption.

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